

Data augmented MCMC for longitudinal rectangular hidden Markov models

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Introduction

Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) (Bartolucci et al., 2012) are latent variable models frequently used to analyze panel data in various real-world contexts. Possible extensions are rectangular HMMs where the number of latent states can change at each time occasion (Russo et al., 2024).

In the Bayesian framework, parameter estimation for latent variable models typically employs Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithms. In this work, we consider the problem of Bayesian estimation of rectangular HMMs implementing a data augmented MCMC (Tanner and Wong, 1987) scheme in which the posterior distribution is augmented by the latent process.

Methods

The augmented MCMC is initially derived for longitudinal HMMs with time-fixed number of latent states, following the approach proposed by Tancini et al. (2024). Based on Gibbs steps for the latent variables, we implement a reversible jump MCMC (RJMCMC) (Green, 1995), which is required to estimate the varying-dimensional parameters of the rectangular HMM. Diversely to Russo et al. (2024), where a marginal likelihood is used, we consider the complete likelihood, sampling the latent process under the MCMC scheme. The label switching problem (Stephens, 2000) is solved using an identifiability constraint. The model selection is based on the RJMCMC.

Results

The data augmented MCMC algorithm yields accurate results for estimating simulated longitudinal HMMs, where the number of latent states is fixed across all time points. The next step involves implementing

the data augmentation procedure using RJMCMC to enable time-varying latent state support. Finally, we will validate our results using both simulated and real datasets.

References

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